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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
DP	Data Portal
EML	Ecological Metadata Language
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
ID	Identifier
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
MDC	MetaData Catalogue
MOD	Metadata for Ontology Description and Publication
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PID	Persistent identifier
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST API	REpresentational State Transfer API
RI	Research Infrastructure
ROR	Research Organization Registry
SA	Semantic Artefact
SAC	Semantic Artefact Catalogue
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
T4.5	EOSC FAIR-IMPACT project's Task 4.5
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	EOSC FAIR-IMPACT project's Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1. Introduction

This report describes work under the FAIR-IMPACT project WP4/T4.5 FAIR semantic artefacts in use within data repositories, and its main focus points: to demonstrate the feasibility of setting up a connector (Semantic Artefacts Catalogues - SACs x (meta)data repository) and to provide concrete evidence of the added value provided by these SAs for the FAIRness of the scientific data stored in the repositories. A number of use cases (UCs) from different scientific disciplines (agri-food, life sciences, ecology, technical and physical sciences, archaeology, Social Sciences and Humanities, astronomy) and operating at different scales and in different research infrastructures (RI) were examined. They identified the semantic needs of their respective communities and the state of progress and organisation of the semantic representation of knowledge in their environments. Connectors have been (or will be) incorporated into (meta)data repositories depending on :

- Metadata that can be semanticised
- SAs and SACs available in the community
- The technologies used by (meta)data repositories and by SAs and SACs
- The needs and practices of (meta)data repositories users: data users, depositors and managers

1.1 Milestone objectives

Throughout the FAIR-IMPACT project, each UC worked individually on setting up connectors, improving or producing relevant SAs and SACs for each community. Follow up meetings were held to report on the progress of each case and to share feedback. Descriptions of all the T4.5 UCs, their challenges and how their connectors were implemented can be found on the FAIR-IMPACT website¹ and on Zenodo.² *Deliverable D4.6 'UC driven validation of semantic artefact exploitation within data repositories'*³ presents these cases in a more standardised way, based on common challenges, and includes consolidated feedback and points to take into account when setting up a connector.

The aim of milestone *M4.5 Internal and external use case evaluation and demonstrators* is to provide evidence of UCs work in the FAIR-IMPACT context, to present the preliminary results of the study related to the impact of the introduction of connectors to SACs in (meta)data repositories, particularly on the data FAIRness. Since connections were only introduced a few months prior to the report, the findings that are shown are not entirely comprehensive; thus, the expected results are also described in depth. Figures resulting from collective work to measure the impact are presented for each UC in the appendices. They present the relevant impact factors to be taken into account, in line with the UC respective challenges.

1.2 Milestone verification means

¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/use-cases>

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/fair-impact/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

³ Aubin, S., & Corre, C. et al.(2025). D4.6 - Use case driven validation of semantic artefact exploitation within data repositories. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14917164>

In line with the milestone verification means “Internal and external use case evaluation, demonstrators with D4.5, and D4.6 available”, the present report provides evidence of work carried out by each UC within T4.5. The realisations can be:

- Participation in regular follow up meetings with regards to the use cases and demonstrators
- Participation in collective task activities:
 - Stakeholder homogenisation work
 - Demonstration session at the FAIR-IMPACT All Hand Meeting 2023
 - Materials feeding the impact study
- UC description writing and publication on the FAIR-IMPACT website
- Contribution to relevant outputs
- Connectors’ code availability in a public repository

The initial vision at the proposal stage included elements for the demonstrators in relation to validation of semantic artefact exploitation within data repositories and mappings. The work towards mappings in the duration of the project identified methodologies and practices around mapping thanks to workshops and a survey to collect ‘use cases’, which led to recommendations for FAIR mapping.⁴ Although UC members actively participated in the workshops and, as such, provided input for the creation of the recommendations, the development of their SAs and SACs happened simultaneously with the publishing of the recommendations, which did not allow exploitation of the final set of recommendations in the duration of the project. With the connectors from SACs and (meta)data repositories are in place, it is simpler to consider mapping exploitation. A workshop on Moving towards FAIR Mappings: from technical recommendations to common practices is planned to take place in May 2025.⁵

1.3 T4.5 results

Eleven targeted meetings provided the opportunity for an average of 7 UCs to be represented each time. Additional one-to-one meetings were organised to further discuss individual UC objectives and challenges.

The results of the **work on stakeholders harmonisation** initiated during the FAIR-IMPACT All Hands Meeting 2023⁶ are presented in Appendice [5.1](#). The collaborative part of the work was based on a Klaxoon board⁷ provided by INRAE. The aim of this work was to share UCs definitions of people implicated and impacted by the connectors between SAC and (meta)data repositories and, secondly, to harmonise terms used to name them, based on a common framework.

⁴ Le Franc, Y., GRAU, N., Juty, N., Mejias, G., Reed, P., Ramezani, P., Poveda-Villalon, M., Garijo, D., Goble, C., & van Horik, R. (2025). D4.5 - Guidelines and methodology to create, document and share mappings and crosswalks. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15106494>

⁵<https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/moving-towards-fair-mappings-technical-recommendations-common-practices>

⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/all-hands-meeting-hague>

⁷ <https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Klaxoon>

The FAIR-IMPACT All Hand Meeting 2024⁸ allowed to organise a **demonstration session** of the developments implemented in the project: connectors implemented (PHIS-AgroPortal, LifeWatchMDC&DP-EcoPortal, DANS Data Stations, EaSyData-EarthPortal, Recherche Data Gouv-AgroPortal) or connectors' mockup (AnaEE-AgroPortal, ArcheoAMU). The slides from the session are available on Zenodo.⁹

The impact study, is the study, or assessment, of the use of SAs in the (meta)data repositories. The common work enabled us to identify what the connectors have impacted and how. Due to the recent implementation of the connectors, this part is still in progress. The preliminary results are presented in parts [2](#) and [3](#) of this milestone and the material used to share and discuss the ideas of UCs are presented in Appendice [5.2](#).

Eight UCs have written and published a **description** of their context and challenges between August 2024 and January 2025. Available on the FAIR-IMPACT uses cases webpage¹⁰ and the "cards" version on Zenodo (cf: Table 1) and gathered in a booklet.¹¹

A second UC description, written later (december 2024), shorter and more harmonised is available in the **D4.6**¹² (T4.5 deliverable) to which the 9 UCs contributed. In the present report, appendice [5.2](#) presents the pictures (screenshots and mockups) of the connectors or SAC developed (or that will be developed) in the project.

Finally, the connectors or SAC source codes and their documentation are available in table 1.

⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/second-all-hands-meeting-hague-15-17-october-2024>

⁹ Aubin, S., Bellot, P., Seinturier, J., Tykhonov, V., Rosati, I., NESTOLA, E., Ramezani, P., Alviset, G., Christelle, P., pichot, . christian ., Clastre, P., Szabo, D., Cabrera-Bosquet, L., Jonquet, C., & Corre, C. (2025, mars 10). FAIR-IMPACT AHM - T4.5 Use cases demonstration session. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14998828>

¹⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/use-cases>

¹¹ Stories of practical implementation of the FAIR principles

https://fair-impact.eu/sites/default/files/2025-02/UseCases_Stories_A4_February2025.pdf

¹² Aubin, S., Corre, C., et al. (2025). D4.6 - Use case driven validation of semantic artefact exploitation within data repositories. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14917164>

Table 1 : T4.5 UCs list

Use case (scientific domain)	Leader organisation	Data repository	Semantic Artefact catalog	Use case description	connector' code
PHIS-AgroPortal (Life sciences)	INRAE	Phenotyping Hybrid Information System	AgroPortal	Enabling interoperability between AgroPortal and PHIS information system data repository for enhanced phenomics data annotation and exchange	https://github.com/OpenSILEX/opensilex
LifeWatch DP&MDC-EcoPortal (Life sciences, ecology)	LifeWatch ERIC & CNR	LifeWatch Metadata catalogue & Data Portal	EcoPortal	Improving ecological (meta)data FAIRness through semantic services: integration of EcoPortal in LifeWatch Italy new platforms	Not available at the time of writing; implementation through ongoing national project ¹³
DANS Data Stations (SSH, Physics & Technical Sciences, Life Sciences, Archeology)	DANS Data Stations	DANS data repositories	SKOSMOS Datastations Vocabularies	FAIR vocabularies in DANS Data Stations	https://github.com/gdcc/dataverse-external-vocab-support
EaSyData-EarthPortal (Earth & environmental sciences)	Data Terra (CNRS)	Earth System Data repository	EarthPortal	Enhance the semantic functionality of the national Earth & Environmental Data Repository by integrating it with the EarthPortal	https://tinyurl.com/Connector-EaSyData-EarthPortal
Recherche Data Gouv-AgroPortal (Life sciences)	INRAE	Recherche Data Gouv (Data INRAE)	AgroPortal	Leveraging AgroPortal ontologies to ease metadata completion and data discovery in Data INRAE	https://github.com/gdcc/dataverse-external-vocab-support/blob/main/examples/keywordsUsingOntoPortal.md
IVOA Astronomy (Physical & technical sciences)	Observatoire de Paris	NA	Astronomy OntoPortal	Semantic Artefacts Alignment for Improving Interoperability in Astronomy	reused: (SAC code, not connector's code) https://ontoportal.github.io/documentation/
AnaEE-AgroPortal (Life Sciences)	INRAE	SemData	AgroPortal	AnaEE use case: Semantic interoperability in ecosystem studies	Not available
ArcheoAMU (Archeology)	Aix Marseille University	EPICHERCHELL	PACTOL	Not available	Sources available on demand using a GitLab access: https://gitlab.lis-lab.fr/julien.seinturier/epi2dap

¹³ EU - Next Generation EU Mission 4 “Education and Research” - Component 2: “From research to business” - Investment 3.1: “Fund for the realisation of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructures” - Project IR0000032 - ITINERIS - Italian Integrated Environmental Research Infrastructures System - CUP B53C22002150006 - <https://itineris.cnr.it/about-itineris/the-project/>

Use case (scientific domain)	Leader organisation	Data repository	Semantic Artefact catalog	Use case description	connector' code
Identifiers.org-ROR.org (Life sciences)	EMBL-EBI	identifiers.org	ROR.org	EMBL-EBI - Providing harmonized information about organisations in identifiers.org using ROR registry	https://github.com/identifiers-org/monorepo/tree/master/react-frontend/registry

1.4 Elements considered and impacted by connectors

The work carried out is based on the hypothesis that the (meta)data stored in repositories should be FAIRer thanks to the introduction of SAs in their metadata. The use of SAs should make the metadata richer and increase their quality and quantity. The use of SAs is explicitly recommended in the FAIR principles¹⁴ (particularly in I2: (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles). The implementation of connectors enables the generalisation of the use of SAs in (meta)data repositories, and initiates reflection on the way to do it. This section describes the various elements involved and impacted by the connection: (meta)data repositories, FAIR SAs, SACs and stakeholders.

1.4.1 (Meta)data repositories

(Meta)data repositories are a centralised place to hold data, share publicly, and organise them in a logical manner.¹⁵ In this context, these repositories are able to store scientific research data and/or metadata about varied scientific domains (environmental sciences, ecology/biodiversity, agri-food, earth, astronomy, archeology and SSH domains). They are built on diverse but sometimes generic technologies like Dataverse, GeoNetwork, DSpace, OpenSILEX, and are developed at the disciplinary and/or national levels. These data repositories are able to host, manage, and share scientific data (text, observations data, genomic data, geolocalised data, survey data, etc.). Data depositors (cf: part 1.3.4 stakeholder) can share their data in these repositories, choosing the accessibility licence and filling a metadata record form. Through the use of adapted technologies, these metadata are standardised and follow schemas like:

- [DDI Lite](#), [DDI 2.5 Codebook](#), [DataCite 4.0](#) for the “Citation Metadata” from [Dataverse](#);
- [Dublin core](#), [ISO 19115/19139](#) (spatial resources), [ISO 19110](#) (feature attribute table), [EML](#) for [GeoNetwork](#);
- [Qualified Dublin Core](#) (QDC) schema and [EML](#) for [DSpace](#);
- [DCAT](#) for RDF data catalogues on the Web;
- [DCAT 3](#) of the DCAT-AP, which is the latest release of the DCAT Application Profile recommended for data portals in Europe.

Metadata describe data or their creation context: keywords, locations, methods and protocols used to obtain the data, software used to obtain or process data, institutions that have produced data, variables names and description associated with observation data, etc.

For data managers and curators of (meta)data repositories, one of the main challenges is to standardise values for these metadata fields. Indeed, the variability can impact data description (metadata) quality, indexation process and limit the capacity of users to find data by using traditional search engines. Another significant problem here is the absence of the basis of the multilingual search functionality as users from various countries can try to search terms in their native language first, and only after that switch to English.

¹⁴ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

¹⁵ <https://datamanagement.hms.harvard.edu/share-publish/data-repositories>

On the data user side, when metadata is filled in with free text, the variability of input (whether by the data depositor or the user searching the database) limits the efficiency of search engines and the relevance of search results. Indeed, depending on the sensitivity of search engines (to caste, to accents) and individual assessments of the spelling or meaning of certain terms, the relevance of results can be challenged very quickly.

The concept of SA and its practical implementations has been developed to overcome these problems.

1.4.2 FAIR Semantic Artefacts

A Semantic Artefact (SA), is defined as “a machine-actionable and -readable formalisation of a conceptualisation enabling sharing and reuse by humans and machines. These artefacts may have a broad range of formalisation, from loose sets of terms, taxonomies, thesauri to higher-order logics.”¹⁶ Across scientific disciplines, SAs are widely used to standardise data representation and description/annotation. Semantic Artefacts are used here to enable the use of terms and concepts in (meta)data repositories. The value of these terms and concepts usually comes from community consensus that confers them an organisation and a definition ideally in several languages. In glossaries, thesaurus and ontologies, terms (and concept in thesaurus, or class in ontology) are often hierarchised from the more general to the more specific. The SA models also allow defining equality, part of, and depreciation relations between SA objects. These relations are used to define SA hierarchy, subdomain-specific groups, synonyms, and translations. Each object can be defined (a statement of the meaning of a term) thanks to a community agreement on definitions.

For each type of SA representation a knowledge schema exists, using different standards and languages¹⁷ as show in figure 1.

¹⁶Le Franc, Y., Parland-von Essen, J., Bonino, L., Lehvälaiho, H., Coen, G., & Staiger, C. (2020). D2.2 FAIR Semantics: First recommendations (1.0). FAIRsFAIR. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5361930>

¹⁷ Yann Le Franc, Luiz Bonino, Hanna Koivula, Jessica Parland-von Essen, & Robert Pergl. (2022). D2.8 FAIR Semantics Recommendations Third Iteration (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6675295>

Various Types of SAs

Zeng 2008 p. 161

Figure 1: Various types of SAs depending on their functions and organisation complexity. Adapted from Zeng, M. L. 2008. Knowledge Organization Systems. Knowledge Organization. 35(2-3), 160-182. <https://doi.org/10.5771/0943-7444-2008-2-3-160>

Semantic artefacts play a pivotal role in implementing the FAIR principles, but it became increasingly apparent that the artefacts themselves also needed to adhere to these principles. They are distributed across the web in a variety of locations and formats. To keep them FAIR and in agreement with web’s standards catalogues were created to host, expose and share semantic artefacts.

1.4.3 Semantic Artefact Catalogues

Semantic Artefact Catalogues (SACs) act as aggregators of semantic artefacts by publishing both the metadata and the content of the semantic artefacts and often providing a search engine and an API (Application Programming Interfaces) to search and access the content through dedicated services. In increasingly communities, SACs allow them to organise SAs and enforce better governance, alignment and sharing of SAs. These SACs are often based on a generic technology such as OntoPortal, Ontology Lookup Service or SKOSMOS in adequation to domains’ specificities, backgrounds and needs. They are able to host a huge amount of SAs and share them through a user interface (users can search and find terms/concepts/classes/instances/properties, or browse and filter SA metadata to discover

and select the right one) or through APIs.¹⁸ The API to search and access content is specific to each SAC which hampers the possibility to access content from multiple sources for use and reuse but also for indexing by search engine. This heterogeneity is due to the diverse metadata schema used by SAC to describe semantic artefacts and the diversity of technology developed. To address this challenge, FAIR-IMPACT works on multiple aspects such as: (i) the development of MOD (a vocabulary to describe SAs) and MOD-API (a specification of a shared API for SACs based on MOD). This work is presented and summarised D4.2¹⁹.

In each UC, the SAC's API is used in (meta)data repositories to access terms and concepts when describing or annotating metadata fields (as "keywords", "materials", "organisms", "locations", etc.) or in the data (to define variables). Within the data repositories, thanks to the connectors developed by the UCs, users are usually able to lookup controlled terms directly in the metadata field with terms-associated information. They can then select controlled terms with clear knowledge of their context and definition and which SA they would be used from. The terms associated with the dataset are then stored in the (meta)data repository dataset record and include a link to the appropriate concept URI in the SAC containing concept description, hierarchy of terms and available translations in other languages, and can then be used for indexing or semantic search. This functionality should enable the enrichment of (meta)data description and improve the data search (and findability) and the overall data FAIRness.

1.4.4 Stakeholders

Seeking a common analysis from UCs of different scientific communities, and different countries who work with data repositories having specific organisation or governance has been a challenge. Measuring the impact of connecting these (meta)data repositories with SACs cannot be limited to dataset findability indicators. To make the experiment more complete and useful to future implementers of a connector, we took into account the impact on human activities as well.

At first, each UC identified their stakeholders and described their respective activities. The terms used to name data stakeholders were so diverse that it was difficult to find commonalities. Therefore, the terms used were harmonised towards the Digital skills for FAIR and open science²⁰ (cf: appendix 1).

From the analysis of the situation provided by the UCs and summarised in Table 2, it turns out that at least six types of data workers interact with keywords or topics associated with data including **researchers, data analysts, citizens, data curators, data stewards/librarians, and research infrastructure professionals**. These include both end users, who either feed or search the data repository, and those involved in the creation and maintenance of information systems.

¹⁸ An API is a software interface that "connects" one program to another

¹⁹ Jonquet, C., & GRAU, N. (2025). D4.2 - FAIR semantic artefact lifecycle from engineering, to sharing (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14643279>

²⁰ <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>

Table 2: main activities x stakeholders impacted by the connection to SAC

Activity / Stakeholder	Citizen	Data analyst	Researcher	Data Curator	Data Steward / Librarian	RI Support Professional
Use terms to search the data	Data users					
Use terms to understand and reuse the data						
Describe data with metadata (keywords, topics...)			Data depositors			
Choose the controlled vocabularies to use in the data space					Data managers	
Develop solutions to manage data and repositories						Data repository provider
Contribute to / create semantic artefact content			SA managers			
Develop solutions to facilitate the use of semantic artefacts						SAC provider

For the needs of this deliverable, six stakeholders groups were drawn, depending on their activities and role:

- **data users** benefit from the results of the connector
- **data depositors** use the connector
- **data managers** customise the connector
- **data repository providers** integrate the connector
- **SA managers** provide up-to-date relevant SA
- **SAC providers** expose SA to the connector

Whenever possible, the UCs questioned and observed people interacting with the system to measure and describe the impact of connecting both data and SA repositories on their activities. In section 2, each UC exposes which stakeholders and activities were considered and how the impact was measured. In section 3, some recommendations are given to (meta)data repositories and SAC providers in particular to facilitate future connectors' implementation in (meta)data repositories.

2. Methodology: how to demonstrate the impact of using SAs in (meta)data repositories

The various methods set up to assess the impact of using SAs in (meta)data repositories will be described. The UCs are based on the principle that using SAs (typically a controlled vocabulary) to describe or annotate (meta)data adds context, disambiguates data and its production context and improves the interoperability of data stored in repositories. **The impact we are seeking to measure assumes that the data will be FAIRer if the metadata characterising them are filled in with vocabularies that are themselves FAIR.** Including and beyond this hypothesis, the impacts expected by the UC leaders can be summarised as :

- Increased findability of the data hosted in the repositories thanks to: 1) increase in the number of controlled terms associated to datasets and 2) the semantic richness of the metadata taken from controlled vocabularies (including synonyms and translations);
- The availability of the SA for the users (data depositors and managers) (SA findability) at the click of the mouse without doing any maintenance effort when the SA changes (versioning) or new SAs have to be used.
- Improved metadata interoperability brought by controlled vocabularies thanks to: 1) the standards representation language used by SAs and their access through shared APIs²¹ that serve them; 2) the mappings between SAs.
- The data reusability due to the better context provided to data, while the SA reusability is due to the highlight of SAC.
- Increased visibility and reuse of SA may limit the proliferation of redundant SA within domains. In particular thanks to the unique interface offered by SACs

To measure and describe these impacts, a variety of strategies, tools and metrics are needed. This part is based on a joint reflection, the materials for which are presented in the appendix 2.

2.1. FAIRness assessment tools

Looking at the role of SA in FAIRness assessment tools is of interest for FAIR-IMPACT, with regards to WP5 activities towards the development of metrics for discipline-specific FAIR assessment, and their implementation.

Following the FAIR principles and deriving FAIRness criteria, a vocabulary is FAIRer if it is registered in a catalogue or a vocabulary server.²² To a certain extent, this FAIRness is inherited by the terms contained in the SA and used in the (meta)data repository.

Two serious candidates were identified to assess dataset FAIRness in the context of this study as they, though partially, take into account the use of FAIR SA in the score as follows:

²¹ See for instance WP4 efforts to develop and promote MOD-API as a shared API for semantic artefact catalogues (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12579778>).

²² Devaraju, A., Huber, R., Mokrane, M., Cepinskas, L., Davidson, J., Herterich, P., L'Hours, H., de Vries, J., & White, A. (2020). FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics (0.3). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3934401>

- **F-UJI**²³ (cf. fig 2) gives a better score if the metadata value is a URI (meaning it is a controlled value, not free text) and if its root namespace is present in a predefined set of SACs e.g., Bioregistry, LOV²⁴, and CESSDA (complete list is available²⁵).
- Similarly, **FAIR-checker**²⁶ (cf. fig 3) verifies that a URI is provided and that the term used is known in either EBI Open Lookup Service, BioPortal, or LOV.

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:
FsF-I2-01M-1	Vocabulary namespace URIs can be identified in metadata	0	1
	comment: The sheer existence of namespaces declared in XML or RDF files is checked here. This test is not scored		
FsF-I2-01M-2	Namespaces of known semantic resources can be identified in metadata	1	3
	test target: http://f-uji.net/vocab/semantic_resource		
	condition: any of members of test target		

Figure 2: F-UJI metrics for FsF-I2-01M - Metadata uses semantic resources

Description:

Weak: FAIR-Checker verifies that at least one used ontology class or property are known in major ontology registries (OLS, BioPortal, LOV)

Strong: FAIR-Checker verifies that all used ontology classes or properties are known in major ontology registries (OLS, BioPortal, LOV)

Figure 3: FAIR-Checker metrics for F2B - Shared vocabularies for metadata

Considering that all SACs used in the present UCs are not recognised as reference resources by the FAIRness assessment tools, the results they provide will be necessarily partial. Note that: (i) OLS and BioPortal are two famous SACs in the biomedical domain, an area in which FAIR-IMPACT’s WP4 had no UC; (ii) LOV is an SAC related to FAIR-IMPACT ‘s partner UPM but was not associated to any T4.5 UCs.

At least two approaches are possible:

- Compute FAIRness scores on the same set of datasets twice, i.e., before and after the introduction of the SAC connector;
- Compare the FAIRness scores of datasets described using terms from SAs with those described with free keywords or terms not from controlled vocabularies.

In both cases, metadata not concerned by the connector must be the same.

²³ <https://www.f-uji.net/index.php?action=home>

²⁴ <https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/>

²⁵ https://f-uji.net/vocab/semantic_resource

²⁶ <https://fair-checker.france-bioinformatique.fr/docs/index.html#>

2.2. Quantitative indicators : Count of ...

To better measure the impact of the connector, a list of metrics of interest were brought by and shared amongst the UCs. They are applicable to either the (meta)data repositories or SACs and tackle findability and reusability.

2.2.1. Indicators from (meta)data repositories

Count of controlled terms / metadata

The **repositories and SA catalogues API** can be used to **count the number of terms associated** with datasets and to evaluate the proportion of these keywords that are referenced in controlled vocabularies (with a URI) vs free text). A similar process can be implemented for other metadata such as software and protocol and variables. **#Findability**

Dataset consultation

Generally, data catalogues and repositories' API or UI (User Interface) provide indicators on the number of consultations of the datasets. Although difficult to relate to the quality of metadata, it should be possible to observe a conjunction between the implementation of connectors and an increase in the number of consultations of datasets using them. The indicators must be collected before and after the connector's introduction. The limitation of this approach is that it ignores other factors that could also have an impact. **#Findability**

Count of reusable semantized objects

In some UCs, e.g., PHIS-AgroPortal, new objects (here variables) are built using terms from SAs. These new objects are then shared with the community (here OpenSilex) to be reused, allowing time and effort saving and more interestingly interoperability. In such a case, **it is possible to count the number of the semantized objects these variables created and that are reused by other members of the community.** **#Reusability**

Count of data reuse / citation

The reusability of data is partly guaranteed by the quality of data referencing and its documentation (context of creation and what is studied). As a long term indicator, it is possible to **compare the number of data citations** (in other resources: articles, studies, projects, datasets, etc.) before and after the enrichment of the metadata using the connector. This indicator can be retrieved using DataCite Commons.²⁷ Given a DOI, this service can indicate other works, publications and datasets, which cite or include references to the dataset identified by this DOI. To be significant, the indicator should be computed for a representative number of datasets in a repository. Also, it is important to note that DataCite Commons requires that data repositories and publication archives properly declare the citations and references. As it is not the case actually, the citation graph is incomplete, which limits the reliability of the indicator. The Global Dataverse community provides

²⁷ <https://support.datacite.org/docs/consuming-citations-and-references>

another similar mechanism for metrics evaluation called Make Data Count²⁸ but it's not being used by the UCs based on Dataverse. **#Reusability**

2.2.2. *Indicators from SACs*

Count of used SA

The **SAC API and/or UI** can be exploited to collect metrics on the SA uses. For instance, in SACs based on OntoPortal, SA consultation is counted with Google Analytics²⁹ This metric counts the SA consultation number, through time and in the SAC. When (meta)data repositories provide a link to the terms hosted in the SAC, the chances that the data repository users access them is augmented. The connector can improve the **consultation number**. **#Accessibility**

Another indication of a SA use is when modifications of the SA are requested by users to fill a gap. When the request feature is available in a SAC or directly in the (meta)data repository UI, it is possible to **count the number of SA modification requests**. **#Reusability**

Count of new SA

In the same way, the **new SA ingested in SAC** to complete the community needs following the users feedback, can be counted. It's a long term indicator of SA appropriation by users and this should make it possible to improve the terms relevance, thus **data findability**.

Count of SA used by a connector

To address the same need, a new SA could easily be added to any connector, thanks to the abstraction offered by the SAC API. This process is possible only if SACs are interoperable (if they used different languages or schema for exemple). The count of the news SAs added to the connector should provide an indicator on the genericity of the connection process. **#Interoperability**

2.3. *Qualitative indicators : interviews*

Users interview

Interviewing users directly can be a good way of assessing the effect of the connectors in place on their practices, e.g., by asking them to evaluate their own ability to exploit SA in the future (through the connectors). Users of catalogues and data repositories are able to assess the quality of search results. **#Findability**

Depositors interview

Data depositors interview: data depositors, who fill in the metadata record and variables associated with their data, can assess their ability to find relevant terms thanks to the connectors, which can also help improve the relevance of the terms and SA proposed. **#Accessibility and Reusability**

²⁸ <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/admin/make-data-count.html>

²⁹ https://ontoportal.github.io/documentation/administration/management/google_analytics_management

SA managers interview

In the same spirit as using SAC's API to assess users' appropriation of SA, SA managers have an essential role to play in taking user feedback into account, to update and modify terms, synonyms and associated definitions. They can therefore assess whether they are getting more feedback, requests for modifications, etc., and if so, what the context of use of their SA is.

3. Main findings and discussion

This section discusses various types of impacts of implementing the connection between SAC and (meta)data repositories.

First, the lever considered in task 4.5 to improve first data FAIRness is the semanticisation of metadata by providing richer metadata and using FAIR vocabularies. Initial evidence of the impact on data FAIRness is provided by UCs but precise meaningful results are still difficult to obtain.

Secondly, thanks to the connectors, data depositors and curators have facilitated access to controlled vocabularies. SACs provide features to use SAs through their APIs. Choosing the best options among those available and good connector settings are two conditions to improve the quality of metadata while making it easier for data depositors and curators in (meta)data repositories. This part presents different approaches adopted by UCs, criteria to choose SAs for the connector and useful information to give to data depositors and curators to select relevant terms.

Finally, we discuss the changes induced by connecting data repositories to SACs, regarding SA management in particular. Sustainability and larger adoption of the connectors are also briefly tackled.

Note that this section details points of vigilance and issues upstream of and arising from the use of SAs hosted in SACs, exposed in D4.6.³⁰ The aim of this feedback is to avoid certain pitfalls and inconveniences for those planning to rely on SACs to handle controlled vocabularies.

3.1. Impact of the connector related to data FAIRness

The main expected impact of the connectors implemented in this task is on the (meta)data repositories themselves, making their content FAIRer, particularly regarding the findability and interoperability aspects.

3.1.1. FAIR SAs can increase the global FAIR scores of datasets

The principle “I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles” applies first to metadata schemas but can also be understood as applying to the semantic artefacts used to

³⁰ Aubin, S., & Corre, C., et al. (2025). D4.6 - Use case driven validation of semantic artefact exploitation within data repositories. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14917164>

fill in metadata values. The I2 principle allows us to assume that the datasets will necessarily be FAIRer thanks to the use of FAIRer SAs (e.g. SAs hosted in SACs) for their metadata. Indeed the use of controlled vocabularies in metadata provide more information, context, and interoperability to (meta)data.

Improve data FAIRness score

In the data repositories, the connector should mainly impact data findability and reusability thanks to the improvement of metadata richness and harmonisation to describe topics, studied organisms, locations, etc. However, it was not always possible to use FAIRness assessment tools to precisely demonstrate this hypothesis.

First, some UCs could not run this evaluation in the timespan of the project. For example, the connection between (meta)data repositories and SACs was established late, therefore no results of improved scores from FAIRness assessment tools were available at the time this report was written. However, the UCs teams expect an increase in FAIRness tool scores in key FAIRness assessment metrics used by the F-UJI tool integrated into the (meta)data repository, particularly:

- FsF-I2-01M: Metadata uses semantic resources: Metadata should incorporate controlled terms from community-specific semantic resources that unambiguously describe the contents so they can be processed automatically by machines;
- FsF-I3-01M: Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities
- FsF-R1-01MD: Metadata specifies the content of the data. [...] Ideally, ontological vocabularies should be used to describe data content (e.g., variable) to support interdisciplinary reuse.

Yet, the IVOA UC reported that FAIRness assessment tools were not able to check relevant metrics in the Astronomy domain. To allow this, the OStrails project³¹ (EOSC supporting project, involving IVOA catalogue and L'observatoire de Paris) aim is to integrate the metadata needed to evaluate FAIR measurements into the astronomical community's ecosystem.

Indeed, F-UJI tests if the metadata value is taken from a SA present in a limited set of SACs including the Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV)³², the Linked Open Data Cloud³³, Bioportal, Bioregistry, CESSDA, FHIR, GESIS, OGC, MMISW, SDN, SEMIC AND SWEET. As these SACs are exposing SAs in non-harmonised ways, the development and maintenance of each connection is costly, which hinders the addition of new sources. This limitation of FAIRness assessment tools was well identified by T5.1³⁴. To be more robust and more inclusive, especially regarding community specific SAs, F-UJI developers are calling for the standardisation of the APIs serving SA metadata. A single entry point to all SA could also be a solution. Once the hurdle is cleared, finer criteria can be conceived to better take into

³¹ <https://ostrails.eu/>

³² <https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/>

³³ <https://lod-cloud.net/>

³⁴ Robert Huber, Maaïke Verburg, Mike Priddy, Hervé L'Hours, Joy Davidson, & Hannah Mihai. (2023). D5.1 Implementing metrics for automated FAIR digital objects assessment in a disciplinary context (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7784120>

account the quality and FAIRness of metadata values, including the FAIRness of the SA they are issued from.

At this stage, it seems complicated to use FAIRness assessment tools as the only metrics to assess the data FAIR score.

3.1.2. *More and richer terms make data more findable*

As FAIRness assessment tools were generally too restrictive, another method was used to measure the data findability. The idea was that datasets defined with SAs are easier to find, resulting in more datasets retrieved by the search engine (recall) and an enhanced ranking based on relevance (precision). Indeed, with a connector to a SAC, terms come with additional information which can be used in search engines and other search features to disambiguate and improve the relevance of retrieved data. In brief, findability of dataset by data users should be improved if:

- The datasets are describe by SAs: the connector is used so metadata are fill in with controlled terms ;
- The search index is able to exploited SAs added value by:
 - searching on terms, synonyms, translations and hierarchy;
 - by giving datasets specified with SAs more weight in the search ranking results.

Concerning the number of metadata containing terms from SA instead of free text, some results from the UCs are shown below:

- For Recherche Data Gouv-AgroPortal UC, since connector introduction (october 2024) 327 datasets were added to the Data INRAE repository, 53.57% containing keywords from controlled vocabularies (against 15.43%, 8.62% and 9.81% in 2023, 2022 and 2021 respectively). It should be noted that providing keywords from SA is not mandatory in the repository.
- There are also various metrics supplied by Dataverse Metrics API available in all DANS Data Stations, providing downloads for every dataset and allowing comparison between metadata with SA and without.

To have a real effect on findability, the increase of records indexed by terms issued from SACs must be combined with an evolution of the search engine strategy. Repository managers must consider changing the parameters of the repository search engine : index terms and their synonyms, exploit SA hierarchies or allow cross-lingual searches.

- For example, the Dataverse ranking is based on Solr³⁵ indexing engine to calculate the weights of a result. The customisation for the DANS UC is given in appendix 3: “keyword” has a weight of 110, lower than title, description and collection metadata. DANS has extended Dataverse functionality to address this issue in the ODISSEI project:³⁶ they extended the search index with multilingual terms coming from SACs, but this functionality is highly experimental and isn’t available for the Dataverse

³⁵ <https://solr.apache.org/>

³⁶ <https://odissei-data.nl/>

community and Data Stations.

The Recherche Data Gouv-AgroPortal UC will also adapt the parameters of the indexing engine to give more weight to the keyword's value and associated information.

Lastly, the dataset consultation number was considered to estimate findability by comparing scores before and after the connector implementation. The short time between the connectors' implementation and the end of the project did not allow UCs to use this approach.

3.1.3. Information systems gain in semantic interoperability

Exchanging data from one IS (Information System) to another is facilitated by standard metadata schema and crosswalks. But it remains difficult to integrate metadata showing free text values. The use of controlled terms hosted in a SAC can facilitate the process³⁷ by offering more flexibility in metadata export or exposition. SACs record all the information about a term which can be accessed through its URI. With this mechanism, the information exchanged by two IS can be limited to this URI. Actually, IS exchanges more information which depends on the export formats and APIs implemented in the IS and on users' needs.

Concretely, introducing a connector to a SAC will, in most of the cases, necessitate changes in the way to store, export and expose metadata values as potentially complex elements instead of free text.

So depending on the export 'formats' offered by the interface, the information exported may be more or less complete. As shown in table 3, the UCs have made different choices in the metadata export to include term-associated information according to the existing export format and the UC requirement. The export was carefully considered in the UC, like AnaEE-AgroPortal and PHIS-AgroPortal, which developed workflows for exporting their data and metadata to other catalogues and repositories.

³⁷ See semantic interoperability recommendations: Tanderup, N., Nygaard Bai, B., Fink, A. S., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gonzalez, E., & van Kemenade, J. (2024). M6.1 Outcome of testing components to achieve core technical & semantic interoperability in cross-domain use cases (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10940164>

Table 3: Changes in metadata export according to export formats and UC choices

Export format	SA information it may contain	Repositories which offers it	example (changes to include SAs information)
OAI_ORE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Value - Vocabulary name - Vocabulary URL - Term URI - Term Name in all languages - Synonyms in all languages 	Recherche Data Gouv, DANS	<pre>{ "citation:keywordValue": "Bombus", "citation:keywordVocabulary": "INRAETHES", "citation:keywordVocabularyURI": "http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/thesaurusINRAE", "citation:keywordTermURL": { "@id": "http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/c_24095", "termName": { "en": "Bombus", "fr": "Bombus" }, "vocabularyUri": "https://data.agroportal.lirmm.fr/ontologies/INRAETHES", "synonyms": { "fr": ["bourdon"], "en": ["bumble bee", "bumblebee"] } } }</pre>
DataCite	None	Recherche Data Gouv, DANS, EaSyData	NA
OpenAIRE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Value - Vocabulary name - Vocabulary URL 	Recherche Data Gouv, DANS	<subject schemeURI="http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/thesaurusINRAE" subjectScheme="INRAETHES">Bombus</subject>
Schema.org JSON-LD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Value 	Recherche Data Gouv, DANS	"keywords":["Agricultural Sciences", "Rattus", "muskrats", "Bombus"]
DDI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Value - Vocabulary name - Vocabulary URL 	Recherche Data Gouv, DANS	<keyword vocab="INRAETHES" vocabURI="http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/thesaurusINRAE">Bombus</keyword>

Dublin Core	- Value	Recherche Data Gouv, DANS	<dcterms:subject>Bombus</dcterms:subject>
Codebook HTML DDI	- Value	Recherche Data Gouv, DANS	Study scope → Keywords: Agricultural Sciences, Rattus, muskrats, Bombus
JSON	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Value - Vocabulary name - Vocabulary URL - Term URI - Term Name in all languages - Synonyms in all languages 	Recherche Data Gouv, DANS, EaSyData	<pre>{ "keywordValue": { "typeName": "keywordValue", "multiple": false, "typeClass": "primitive", "value": "hydrological intermittence" }, "keywordTermURL": { "typeName": "keywordTermURL", "multiple": false, "typeClass": "primitive", "value": "http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/c_da2ed596", "expandedvalue": { "@id": "http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/c_da2ed596", "termName": { "en": "hydrological intermittence", "fr": "intermittence hydrologique" } }, "vocabularyUri": "https://data.agroportal.lirmm.fr/ontologies/INRAETHES", "synonyms": [] } }, "keywordVocabulary": { "typeName": "keywordVocabulary", "multiple": false, "typeClass": "primitive", "value": "INRAETHES" }, "keywordVocabularyURI": { "typeName": "keywordVocabularyURI", "multiple": false, "typeClass": "primitive", "value": "http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/thesaurusINRAE" } }</pre>
XML	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Value - Vocabulary name - property URI - Term URI 	LifeWatch, EaSyData	<pre><keywordSet> <keyword>Alien species</keyword> <keywordThesaurus>Alien Species Thesaurus</keywordThesaurus> </keywordSet> [...] <annotation> <propertyURI label="keyword">http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#keyword</propertyURI> <valueURI label="Alien species">https://kos.lifewatch.eu/thesauri/alienspecies/c_1</valueURI> </annotation></pre>

JSON-LD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Value - Vocabulary name - Property URI - Term URI 	LifeWatch	<pre> {"@context": { "@vocab": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#", "keywordSet": { "@id": "https://schema.org/keywords" }, "keywordThesaurus": "https://schema.org/CreativeWork", "propertyURI": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#keyword", "valueURI": "@id" }, "@type": "Dataset", "keywordSet": [{ "keyword": "Alien species", "keywordThesaurus": "Alien Species Thesaurus" }], "annotation": [{ "propertyURI": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#keyword", "label": "keyword" }, "valueURI": { "@id": "https://kos.lifewatch.eu/thesauri/alienspecies/c_1", "label": "Alien species" } }] } </pre>
RDF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Value - Vocabulary name - Property URI - Term URI 	EaSyData, AnaEE	<pre> ... <rdf:Description rdf:about="http://opendata.inrae.fr/anaeeThes/c_1437639244292"> <dcat:theme rdf:resource="http://opendata.inrae.fr/anaeeOnto#EcosystemType"/> <skos:prefLabel>forest ecosystem</skos:prefLabel> </rdf:Description> </rdf:RDF> </pre>

3.2. Metadata fill in is facilitated by SAs accessibility for data depositors and curators

To improve the SA effect (findability and interoperability) in the (meta)data repositories, SAs need to be used. To optimise the use of SA, the parameters of the connectors must be oriented towards the needs and practices of (meta)data repositories' users. Various connector settings were implemented in the UCs according to the data depositors, managers and curators' needs. First, in this section, we present the three features explored in the task: autocompletion, tree navigation and annotator, and their impacts on the users' practices and UI ergonomics. Secondly, we explore criteria for selecting SAs to connect to a (meta)data repository, regarding quantity and quality of these SAs. Finally, we discuss the useful information from SAs to expose to data depositors and curators to select a term.

3.2.1. Guidance and assistance to fill in metadata

Concretely, three types of features have been added to the repositories to provide assistance to data depositors and curators to select a term from a SAC: autocompletion, tree navigation and automatic term extraction from dataset textual description (e.g. "annotator").

Autocompletion consists in a search bar which suggests terms corresponding to the character string entered by the user. Corresponding terms are retrieved through the API and selected by repository users. Recherche Data Gouv-AgroPortal, PHIS-AgroPortal, LifeWatch DP-EcoPortal and DANS Data Stations have implemented this feature for variables, keywords, software and protocol metadata (cf. appendix figure 12, 4 & 8, respectively). Autocompletion, though easy to use, requires from the user to have an idea of the terms they are looking for, and of what is expected in the metadata in question. This raises several questions including:

- the information to be associated with the term to enable the user to make a choice;
- the adequacy of the SA proposed to fill in the metadata item.

The LifeWatch MDC-EcoPortal UC chose to use the tree navigation. Tree navigation also consists of a search bar that suggests terms corresponding to the character string entered by the user, but the terms are suggested in each SA and their hierarchical context is shown. In addition, they make a choice to add a popup to give access to other terms-associated information (cf appendix figure 6). The main limitation of this feature is the quantity of information provided to the user: it can be very time-consuming to choose a term taking into account all information.

The UCs EaSyData-EarthPortal and AnaEE-AgroPortal (cf. appendix figure 10 & 16) chose to use the "annotator" available in SA portals from the OntoPortal suite. This functionality, accessible with the API, suggests terms on the basis of the information provided by the user (description of the dataset, its title, etc.) and the vocabularies selected in the connector. The terms proposed by the API are automatically added to the record. In a second step, the data

depositor or curator must decide whether the term is suitable or not. This process greatly simplifies and accelerates the addition of controlled vocabularies to metadata. However, it is very dependent on the quality of the annotator and of the text input.

To each connector feature, the UI ergonomics is critical to improve the SAs use in (meta)data repositories. Indeed, the metadata forms should be as simple as possible. The connectors need to facilitate access to SA and make filling faster and users friendly. To assess this aspect, the best contacts are the connectors users themselves (e.g. data depositors and curators). However, in some UCs this was not possible due to the recent implementation of the connection between the platforms. Nevertheless, some UC, as LifeWatchDP&MDC-EcoPortal, will be scheduled in the near future to assess how the connectors improve SA accessibility and make metadata entry faster and more intuitive.

In the Recherche Data Gouv-AgroPortal case, data depositors can select keywords from five SAs, using autocompletion in the dataverse repository. Through semi-directed remote interviews, stakeholders (depositors and users) were asked questions and required to complete a "mission," the success of which was evaluated.

Profile	Mission type / Questions to the tester	Results
Data depositors	Mission : Create a dataset, fill in associated metadata and particularly the keyword part	
	Do you know which keywords you want to associate with your dataset? Do you understand where you need to add these keywords? Do you find relevant terms, according to your expectations? Why have you chosen that term, in that vocabulary? Which term-associated information was the most useful to choose?	They don't always know in advance which terms they want as keywords. They are able to select a term via the connector. They don't always know which language to use for their keywords. They are not familiar with the proposed SA, and often select the institutional thesaurus (trustworthy resource).
Conclusion: Data depositors want to consult the SA to find relevant terms (hierarchy, synonyms and definition), but don't want to question the reliability of their SA. Terms-associated information directly available in the metadata record are crucial to select a term.		

3.2.2. Which SAs should be accessible : SAs quality and quantity

Always to improve SA accessibility and use in (meta)data repositories, their quality regarding community needs and practices and their quantity regarding complementarity and relevance are critical. In this section, we discuss the possibility to use the FAIRness assessment tools for Ontology and other criteria to take into account to improve SAs relevance to connectors.

FAIRness assessment tool for Ontology

In the case of vocabularies hosted in OntoPortal instances (AgroPortal, EarthPortal, EcoPortal), the FAIRness assessment tool for ontology, O'FAIRe, is implemented and makes it possible to assess the FAIRness of vocabularies. This FAIRness assessment tool is based on

FAIR principle and different FAIRness assessment state-of-the-art initiatives, to produce a grid applicable to various SA. The score is established thanks to 61 questions/tests,³⁸ and normalised around the 15 FAIR principles. It's able to define a clear generic and customisable methodology to automatically assess the FAIRness level of ontologies, guide semantic stakeholders to make their semantic resources FAIR, and select relevant FAIR semantic resources for use. Eighty percent of the score is based on the ontology metadata description, because clear metadata descriptions and open semantic repositories are two key elements of making semantic resources FAIR.³⁹

One of the main ways to improve SA FAIRness is their storage in SAC. Indeed, to host SA, SAC required strict and complete metadata that ensured a minimum FAIR score, for example in AgroPortal, following MOD 3.0 recommendations⁴⁰.

In addition to the criteria mentioned above, other criteria must be taken into account to assess the reliability and quality of the vocabulary of interest:

What is its metadata schema?

From one SAC to another or depending on the SA themselves, the metadata schemas are not equivalent. However, it is necessary to ensure that a minimum amount of information is associated with SA. In particular, to correctly identify the needs that they are able to meet and to ensure that the information can be consulted by all users. This information can be used to make feedback and to inform users to the nature of the SA content (scientific domain, knowledge domain represented)

In what form is it represented: is it an ontology, a thesaurus, a lexicon?

The form of the vocabulary (the classes and properties that make it up) makes it possible to add a level of complexity and information: this determines the quantity and quality of existing relationships between terms and concepts: hierarchy, translation, synonyms, etc.

This level of complexity (or richness) must be consistent with the domain of knowledge it represents, as well as with the semantic needs previously established (e.g. some metadata can be filled with less semantized vocabularies). For example, according to the RI type and scale, the need can be a list of organisms or a complex ontology able to represent a knowledge domain.

How many SAs to address the community needs?

In addition to the nature of the SA, their number needs to be questioned. If one SA cannot cover all the data repository thematic perimeter, several SAs need to be proposed in the

³⁸ <https://github.com/agroportal/fairness/blob/master/doc/results/FAIR-questions.md>

³⁹Amdouni, E., Bouazzouni, S., Jonquet, C. (2022). O'FAIRe: Ontology FAIRness Evaluator in the AgroPortal Semantic Resource Repository. In: Groth, P., et al. The Semantic Web: ESWC 2022 Satellite Events. ESWC 2022. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 13384. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-11609-4_17

⁴⁰Gonzalez Beltran, A. N., & Wilson, A. (2024). M4.3 - Specification of semantic artefact description. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10725304>

connector. Ideally, they should be complementary, relevant to the users of each IS and not overlap. For the UC presented here, it is easier to start from the existing SA in each community, then to identify where they are stored (in which SAC) and finally to make the link with the semantic needs that have been identified in each repository. In some communities, not all the SA are stored in the same catalogue, or are not stored at all in SAC, in these cases SACs are essential to centralised the existing options. This means that either a pooling effort needs to be made, or that connectors need to be put in place with several catalogues.

In the UC Recherche Data Gouv-AgroPortal, 5 SAs were selected: the INRAE thesaurus, which covers all the institute's fields in a very generic way, the AGROVOC thesaurus, which contains terms from the agri-food sector in a large number of languages, the NCBI taxon, which covers the names of biological organisms, and the AnaEE thesaurus and PO2/transformon ontology, which offers more specific terms related to measurement methods and field experimentation techniques. In the case of IVOA Astronomy, vocabularies have been imported with very little modification (already in RDF), for the other astronomy sub-communities. Terms and vocabularies was converted into ontologies that can be ingested into Astronomy Ontoportale (developed during the project, cf. appendix figure 14). This is work in progress, with the communities to develop and adopt those new semantic artefacts. In the case of DANS Data Stations, the connector currently in place in the Social Sciences and Humanities and archeology dataverse is connected to SKOSMOS, and they would like to set up another connector, with AgroPortal for the life sciences dataverse in particular. More specific cases such as PHIS-AgroPortal and AnaEE-AgroPortal use vocabularies that respond directly to the needs of their repositories: the Crop Ontology, on which the PHIS variable model is based, and the AnaEE thesaurus, which were created specifically to meet the needs of the users of this infrastructure.

3.2.3. Provide the necessary and sufficient information to the depositor

The information made available to data depositors and curators in the data repositories interface must enable them to select the relevant term. Depending on the SA proposed in the connector, more or less information associated to the term can be provided to assess relevance:

- Its labels, including synonyms and translations give an indication of the meaning of the term;
- Its hierarchy (or other links) can precise the meaning of the term;
- Its definition, when available, ensures that the term is the one expected (regardless of the common/community meaning);
- The name of the SA from which it is issued gives more information on the domain or the community/institution who created it. This is particularly useful when the user has to choose a term present in several SAs.

This information can be made available directly in the metadata record of the (meta)data repository, at the risk of making the interfaces visually cumbersome. Another solution is to

give the user a link to the SA. The SAC then provides the complete information and context of the term and also allows users to navigate within the SA. A mix of both approaches allows the data managers to find the right balance between information immediately accessible via the repository interface and information accessible by visiting the SAC.

In Recherche Data Gouv the data depositor can show the Preferred name of his tapping term, the vocabulary name and can access to the term in AgroPortal through a link on the selected term. It means that if a user wants to choose a term depending on its classification or synonyms, he has to select the term and follow the link to consult AgroPortal. During user interviews, some people notice that they don't know the terms or vocabulary to choose. To the depositor view: they would like to access hierarchy/classification, to know the subdomain and the terms' definition. They also want to compare available vocabularies to make better choices.

The same questions must be asked of data users, who consult the records. What information do they need to correctly interpret what the applicants have wished to communicate? And how should they obtain this information?

Here again, we need to look at the information that needs to be made available to users so that they can understand the search engine results and assess the relevance of the dataset for their needs. Depending on the infrastructure, users may have access in the record to a link to the term in its vocabulary or in the SAC that hosts it, or they may have access directly in the record to more information (broader term, synonym, definition).

3.3. SA are better considered for data management and sharing

Already in 2018, in its report "Turning FAIR into reality", the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data acknowledged the need to "Support semantic technologies - Semantic technologies are essential for the interoperability and need to be developed, expanded and applied both within and across disciplines".⁴¹ The FAIR IMPACT project allowed to bring major advances on technologies including SACs, APIs for SAs but also on community best practices and governance.

Beyond the impact on (meta)data repositories, the introduction of connectors enables a form of popularisation of SAs in the scientific community by providing links to them. As discussed above, SACs make them easily accessible and discoverable by the different stakeholders involved in data management. They can also facilitate discussion between SA providers and final users. With the foreseen intensified use of SAs in (meta)data repository users and their mutualisation in SACs, improvements in their life cycle and governance are needed. This section also addresses the connectors' sustainability and larger adoption.

3.3.1. The connector raises awareness and interest towards SA

⁴¹ European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data, 2018, p.4

The connector should induce an increased consultation of connected SAs, thanks to the link associated to the terms in records or in the metadata form. This increase was observed but only at a small scale in some UCs.

Figure 4: Visitation number in AgroPortal of 5 stored SAs, implicated in Recherche Data Gouv-AgroPortal connector.

These data are extracted from AgroPortal UI and based on Google analytic, they don't count the visitation in original SA interfaces and count the number of SA visitors monthly. TRANSFORMON: PO2/TransformON Ontology, AnaEETHES: AnaEE Thesaurus, INRAETHES: INRAE Thesaurus, NCBITAXON: NCBI TAXON taxonomy, and AGROVOC: Agrovoc Thesaurus.

For some UCs however, this impact could not be observed for two different reasons: the SAC did not pre-exist the connector (no possible comparison) or the connector was implemented very recently, so the change in the SA consultation rate is not significant.

Precisely assessing the effect of a connector on the SAC popularity would require an in-depth analysis of SACs logs.

From the user interviews, it appears that SACs facilitate the appropriation of the SAs by non-specialists by:

- providing an harmonised interface for SA users of a community;
- providing advanced features to search, browse and use SAs;
- providing features to request for SA modification;
- presenting other SAs of interest to the user;
- enforcing the standardisation of their formats and associated-metadata, making them easier to understand and reuse.

In addition, the connector, by highlighting the interface of a SAC as the single interlocutor for a large number of users, can encourage the ingestion of new SA in these SAC.

The update of SAs used in the connector can also be an indicator of users' appropriation. In the long run, users' feedback can improve the accuracy of SAs by suggesting the addition of terms that are useful to the community or, on the contrary, point out terms that should be deprecated. Users can also influence the richness and quality of information associated with each term included in connected SAs. This effect can only be demonstrated over the long term.

Taking into account the users feedback in the SA evolution and improvement implies a clear governance and communication needs between SA users and their authors.

3.3.2. Improvements on SA management and governance are needed

The UCs present different types of organisation and governance regarding SA and SACs. While EaSyData-EarthPortal, DANS Data Stations and IVOA Astronomy created the SAC for their community and manage the hosted SAs in a centralised manner, other UCs rely on community SACs managed by tiers. In both cases, SAC and SA managers need to set up the conditions to support data managers and end users in their activities including:

- choosing relevant and trustworthy SAs to connect to the data repository;
- providing feedback on SA quality and ability to cover their needs for terms, definitions, etc;
- adapting to technical changes and evolving recommendations.

For instance, PHIS-AgroPortal considers the possibility to suggest terms and mappings to AgroPortal hosted SAs directly from their interface.

SACs can play the role of facilitator first by providing up-to-date versions of SAs, inviting SA managers to provide detailed information on the engineering methodologies and standards used, the existence of an editorial board, the conditions for asking SA modifications and means for contributing to the content if ever possible. SACs can also provide pedagogical content and training sessions.

Such aspects have been little addressed by the UCs but have been identified by some of them as challenges or perspectives.

Task 4.1 of the FAIR IMPACT project analysed a variety of methodologies and practices for SA creation, development, publication, maintenance and sustainability ("Semantic artefact governance models and disciplinary approaches for inclusion within EOSC", D4.1⁴²). They produced governance recommendations that can be considered by the UCs to address their specific needs in the future. In particular, they consider the degree of centralisation of the SA governance which can be very different across or even within UCs.

⁴²Ramezani, P., Grau, N., Jonquet, C., & Fiore, N. (2024). D4.1 - Semantic artefact governance models and disciplinary approaches for inclusion within EOSC (v2 - DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142842>

3.3.3. Ensuring the connector's sustainability and larger adoption

In the EOSC FAIR-IMPACT WP6 Interoperability, M6.1 Outcome of testing components to achieve core technical & semantic interoperability in cross-domain use cases⁴³ discussed EOSC component interoperability through the production of recommendation/checklist including the semantic interoperability of systems. The connectors developed in T4.5 are a valuable solution to address these recommendations.

The interdependence created between the (meta)data repository and a tiers infrastructure introduces constraints or requirements, starting with the commitment of SACs to ensure continuity of service.

In the long term, each UC is committed to maintain the connector and ensure its sustainability taking into account the evolutions of both connected parties, i.e. the meta(data) repository and the SAC.

For instance, the MOD-API for SACs⁴⁴ (Metadata for Ontology Description and Publication Ontology Application Program Interface) was designed in the EOSC FAIR-IMPACT project to provide unified access to the catalogue content (i.e., the artefacts, their distribution and their records), enabling seamless querying and use by stakeholders independent of domain. The MOD-API is formalised by means of an OpenAPI template⁴⁵ designed to guide the implementation of Web REST APIs.⁴⁶ The UC could not benefit from this new API for their connectors. As SACs will adopt this new model, connectors will need to be adapted. At the end, the standardisation of APIs for SAs will make the connector's maintenance easier and will also facilitate the implementation of more connectors.

This experimentation through UCs at small and medium scale highlighted the advantages of relying on a SAC as well as necessary technical adaptations of (meta)data repositories and changes in management and governance of SAs. Having proved the value of such an approach, some cases are already considering to extend the connector to other warehouses or other communities:

- In the case of DANS, the connector is implemented between a SKOSMOS instance and the SSH and archeology Data Station. The future goal is to have a connection for vocabularies hosted in one or more OntoPortal instances with Data Stations for other communities including Life Sciences and the one for Physical and Technical Sciences.
- In the Recherche Data Gouv-AgroPortal UC, the connector may be extended from Data INRAE to other Recherche Data Gouv collections. It is also configurable using a simple JSON file, allowing each Dataverse installation to select the vocabularies and the metadata fields they want to use. All source code needed to extend the existing

⁴³ Tanderup, N., Nygaard Bai, B., Fink, A. S., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gonzalez, E., & van Kemenade, J. (2024). M6.1 Outcome of testing components to achieve core technical & semantic interoperability in cross-domain use cases (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10940164>

⁴⁴ <https://fair-impact.github.io/MOD-API/>

⁴⁵ <https://spec.openapis.org/oas/v3.1.0#openapi-specification>

⁴⁶ Wilson, A., & Jonquet, C. (2024). D4.3 - Specification of shared metadata description of semantic artefacts and their catalogues including common reference API. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12579779>

feature to support the new connector has been contributed to the Dataverse software codebase.⁴⁷ The connector itself has been published in a dedicated Dataverse community repository⁴⁸ accessible for all to reuse.

- In the ArcheoAMU UC: PACTOL Thesaurus should soon update its API to connect with OpenAPI standard. This technical change of the SAC involved in the connector will require new developments.

To facilitate further adoption within various communities and data ecosystems, all connectors' code should be open source and publically accessible by the end of the FAIR IMPACT project. In addition, the process and methods used to set up the connectors should be properly documented.

⁴⁷ <https://github.com/IQSS/dataverse>

⁴⁸ <https://github.com/gdcc/dataverse-external-vocab-support>

4. Conclusions and next steps

The main outcomes from this milestone report are:

- 9 UCs have implemented or intend to implement a connector between a SAC and a (meta)data repository. The work carried out by each UC is exposed and explained in this report through the various figures, appendixes, and examples.
- Most of the code and documentation of these implementations are available at the time of writing this report. This should facilitate similar implementations in other scientific disciplines or institutional repositories.
- The impact study initiated a collective reflection to provide recommendations to implement new connectors, to test various features, and to improve SAs relevance and accessibility via SACs.

The impact of connectors on the FAIRness of (meta)data has not yet been fully assessed, due to the recent connectors' implementation. But each UC has defined a serious avenue to explore and plan some assessment activities for the next months. Particularly, we commonly notice perspectives on the FAIRness assessment tools improvement (particularly concerning F-UJI, implicated in the FAIR-IMPACT project) and on the SAs and SACs appropriation by end-users, to associate with a sustainable governance model for these SACs.

In addition, one of the main challenges for the UCs in the future is to keep connectors up to date with technical, knowledge domain and standards changes.

The work presented globally addressed its initial goals by connecting (meta)data repositories and SACs serving a variety of communities. It also addressed at least two project specific impacts defined in the proposal:

- Impact #2: Federated research objects in EOSC enabled by better governance of FAIR semantic artefacts;
- Impact #5: Active and engaged research communities and infrastructures supporting the implementation of an open and FAIR EOSC ecosystem).

In terms of commitment, the task exceeded the initial objectives with 9 use cases developed while 6 were originally planned, thus showing a particular interest among the project partners.

5. Appendices

5.1. Identifying and qualifying the stakeholders

To ensure a certain level of understanding and coherence in naming stakeholders in further work, we adopted the following methodology:

- Work face-to-face during the All Hands Meeting (appendix figure 1): participants were asked to indicate on postnotes the names for their stakeholders together with phrases indicating actions or responsibilities in the context of the data repository.
- Using the activities listed by the participants, the stakeholders mentioned in the UCs were mapped to the typology defined by Digital skills for FAIR and open science which also provides definitions reused in this report (appendix table 1)
- Graphical representation of the various definition for each type of stakeholder (appendix figure 2).

Appendix figure 1: AHM board to name and define stakeholders from each UC (present: LifeWatchDP&MDC-EcoPortal with Enrica Nestola and Ilarie Rosati ; Recherche Data Gouv-AgroPortal with Sophie Aubin ; PHIS-AgroPortal with Clement Jonquet; ArcheoAMU with Patrice Bellot; DANS Data Station with Andrea and Ingrid; EasyData-EarthPortal with Guillaume Alviset ; Jana Martínková)

Appendix table 1: Homogenisation of stakeholder description by the various UC present to AHM according to the standardize list from: European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Manola, N., et al., Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>

Actions/responsibilities re semantic artefact (Sophie's proposal)	Harmonized label according to Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science (https://eosc.europa.eu/publication-detail-publication/718076c6114eb-a6e5-01aa75ed71a1#page=6) See definitions in 2d tab	other possible stakeholder	Stakeholder label provided by AHM participant	Other labels provided by AHM participant	Verbaten provided by AHM participant (original data - DO NOT EDIT please)	Provider	Comment
contribute to semantic artefact content	Data Curator		data curator		give feedback for semantic artefacts	Guillaume (Data Tera)	
monitor SA usage in the data repository	Data Curator		data curator		follow usage of their semantic artefacts	Guillaume (Data Tera)	
write or select metadata values	Data Curator		data curator		role facilitated by controlled vocabularies	Guillaume (Data Tera)	
write or select metadata values	Data Curator		data curator	curator	check files, check metadata quality and complete with additional information, interacts with data pro	Sophie (ROO INFRAE)	
write or select metadata values	Data Curator		repository curator		check and add metadata and file formats	Ingrid (DANS)	
create semantic artefacts (incl. metadata schemas)	Data Research Infrastructure Support Pr...		data scientist	computer scientist	invents new (meta)data representations, e.g. RO-CRATE	Andrea (DANS)	e.g. Carole Gobble
define the metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies to use in the data space	Data Research Infrastructure Support Pr...		data space manager	administrateur d'espa	enhances their products driven by use case	Sophie (ROO INFRAE)	
define the metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies to use in the data space	Data Research Infrastructure Support Pr...		data station manager		permanent role to take care of the repository of a domain/discipline, mostly interact with the commu	Andrea (DANS)	
introduce new features in data repository	Data Research Infrastructure Support Pr...		data station manager		permanent role to take care of the repository of a domain/discipline, mostly interact with the commu	Andrea (DANS)	
create semantic artefacts (incl. metadata schemas)	Data Research Infrastructure Support Pr...		ontologist		creates semantic artefacts	Jana (e-SF)	
monitor SA usage in the data repository	Data Research Infrastructure Support Pr...		ontology developer		get feedback and use of their resources in data repositories	Guillaume (Data Tera)	
introduce new features in data repository	Data Research Infrastructure Support Pr...		research data engineer		works on new technological solutions, e.g. including controlled vocabulary in a metadata schema	Andrea (DANS)	e.g. Slava in Dataverse
contribute to semantic artefact content	Data Research Infrastructure Support Pr...		SAC developer		enhances their products driven by use case	Miacon board	
introduce new features in data repository	Data Research Infrastructure Support Pr...		service provider		can build thematic facets to facilitate data discovery	Miacon board	
introduce new features in data repository	Data Research Infrastructure Support Pr...		service provider		can use the same Dataverse - SKOSMOS technique	Miacon board	
use controlled vocabulary values to search the data, analyse the (meta)data	Data Scientist/Data Analyst	Researcher	data consumer		integration of data	Miacon board	
use controlled vocabulary values to search the data, analyse the (meta)data	Data Scientist/Data Analyst	Policy Maker	data consumer		can build thematic indicators to monitor and drive scientific orientations in the institute	Miacon board	
use controlled vocabulary values to search the data, analyse the (meta)data	Data Scientist/Data Analyst		data processor		execute (semi)automatic data quality control	Andrea (DANS)	
use controlled vocabulary values to search the data, analyse the (meta)data	Data Scientist/Data Analyst		data scientist		search and analyse data	Iliana & Enrica (Lefwatch)	
use controlled vocabulary values to search the data, analyse the (meta)data	Data Scientist/Data Analyst		data scientist		usually from computer sciences / mathematics; works with data from a repository, makes new analys	Andrea (DANS)	e.g. Yves Rosenblyck at DANS
write or select metadata values	Data Steward/Data Librarian		data steward	data curator	can move easily core data	Miacon board	
advise on metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies (DMP) advice on metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies	Data Steward/Data Librarian		data manager		advise on structured data	Guillaume (Data Tera)	
advise on metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies (DMP) advice on metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies	Data Steward/Data Librarian		data steward		helps researchers write DMPs	Ingrid (DANS)	
advise on metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies (DMP) advice on metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies	Data Steward/Data Librarian		data steward		create/update the data management plan	Jana (e-SF)	
advise on metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies (DMP) advice on metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies	Data Steward/Data Librarian	Data Curator	data steward	data curator	temporarily assigned role in a project to initiate & control & train for research data management	Andrea (DANS)	e.g. Andrea as part of the musicology research project
write or select metadata values	Data Steward/Data Librarian		data steward		quality control is facilitated by auto-completion	Miacon board	
write or select metadata values	Data Steward/Data Librarian	Data Curator	data steward	data curator	deposits data on behalf of research teams	Ingrid (DANS)	
advise on metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies	Data Steward/Data Librarian		data steward	data curator	can find more SAs to use	Miacon board	
advise on metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies	Data Steward/Data Librarian		repository manager	data station manager	contact depositors / institutions	Ingrid (DANS)	
communicate on the benefits for using controlled vocabularies	Data Steward/Data Librarian	Data Curator	repository manager	data station manager	promote the repository	Ingrid (DANS)	
encourage/impose the use of controlled vocabularies	Data Steward/Data Librarian		repository manager	data station manager	ambassadors for FAIR data	Ingrid (DANS)	
use controlled vocabulary values to analyse the metadata	Data Steward/Data Librarian		repository manager	data station manager	check metadata	Ingrid (DANS)	
advise on metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies	Data Steward/Data Librarian		research data expert		works in projects, mostly in roles to advice on how to make data FAIR	Andrea (DANS)	e.g. in DANS, Pascal Flichr
advise on metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies	Policy Maker		policy maker		ambassadors for (FAIR) depositing data	Ingrid (DANS)	
encourage/impose the use of controlled vocabularies	Policy Maker	Data Research Infrastr...	policy maker		input for governance and standards	Ingrid (DANS)	
develop solutions to facilitate the use of semantic artefacts	Research Software Engineer		SAC developer		offer new ways to browse SA - driven by data (enrichment analysis)	Guillaume (Data Tera)	
use controlled vocabulary values to search the data, analyse the (meta)data	Researcher	Citizens	data consumer		more and also English search terms (currently in Dutch) (maybe - not sure if this use case is feasi	Miacon board	
use controlled vocabulary values to search the data, analyse the (meta)data	Researcher	Data Steward/Data Li...	data consumer		can get interoperable data/metadata	Miacon board	
write or select metadata values	Researcher	Citizens	data consumer		can find more SAs to use	Miacon board	
write or select metadata values	Researcher	Data Steward/Data Li...	data depositor		file out metadata	Ingrid (DANS)	(can be different persons from researcher: self till data steward at university)
write or select metadata values	Researcher	Data Steward/Data Li...	data depositor	depositor (F R)	publishes and manages datasets	Sophie (ROO INFRAE)	
write or select metadata values	Researcher	Data Steward/Data Li...	data depositor		semantic indexing made easier by auto-completion	Miacon board	
write or select metadata values	Researcher	Data Steward/Data Li...	data depositor		easier production of FAIR data	Miacon board	
write or select metadata values	Researcher	Data Steward/Data Li...	data depositor		can use the same Dataverse - SKOSMOS technique	Miacon board	
use controlled vocabulary values to search the data, analyse the (meta)data	Researcher		domain specialist	archeologist	searches for data, make analyses, overviews	Andrea (DANS)	
use controlled vocabulary values to search the data, analyse the (meta)data	Researcher		educator		browse and explore data	Patrice (AMU)	
use controlled vocabulary values to search the data, analyse the (meta)data	Researcher	Citizens	end user		easy discovery for the metadata reference	Guillaume (Data Tera)	
use controlled vocabulary values to search the data, analyse the (meta)data	Researcher	Citizens	end user		semantically enhanced search	Guillaume (Data Tera)	
write or select metadata values	Researcher		research scientist		search/use data for their research	Iliana & Enrica (Lefwatch)	
write or select metadata values	Researcher		research scientist		share/publish data on repository	Iliana & Enrica (Lefwatch)	
write or select metadata values	Researcher		research scientist		structure/harmonize data with semantic artefacts (add/inf in attribute values: metadata schemas with semantic artefacts)	Miacon board	
contribute to semantic artefact content	Researcher		researcher	depositor	creating new knowledge objects when creating data. Get credit back by providing them in publicly s	Miacon board	
write or select metadata values	Researcher		researcher	depositor	don't bother semantically describing their datasets	Miacon board	
write or select metadata values	Researcher	Data Steward/Data Li...	researcher	depositor	more user friendly (meta)data publication process	Miacon board	
write or select metadata values	Researcher	Data Steward/Data Li...	researcher	depositor	more and also English search terms (currently in Dutch) (maybe - not sure if this use case is feasi	Miacon board	
find controlled vocabularies or other semantic artefacts for reuse	Researcher	Data Steward/Data Li...	researcher	depositor	find and/or control vocabularies and thesauri in a single repository	Miacon board	
contribute to semantic artefact content	Researcher		scientist	researcher	define new concepts and populate ontologies	Clément (PHIS)	
use controlled vocabulary values to search the data, analyse the (meta)data	Researcher		scientist	researcher	get semantically enhanced results	Clément (PHIS)	
?			data owner		person/community who owns the dataset (not necessarily produce it)	Jana (e-SF)	
?			data scientist		produce data products and code (algorithm and software)	Iliana & Enrica (Lefwatch)	
write or select metadata values			data scientist	data curator	structure/harmonize data with semantic artefacts (add/inf in attribute values: metadata schemas with	Iliana & Enrica (Lefwatch)	
write or select metadata values			data steward	data curator	can automate key word input by using text mining on dataset description / data files	Miacon board	
?			end user		recommendations	Guillaume (Data Tera)	
contribute to semantic artefact content			ontologist		experts on the domain	Jana (e-SF)	
?			researcher	scientist	controlled metadata restriction	Guillaume (Data Tera)	
?			service provider		further use of Dataverse as SA platform	Miacon board	

Appendix figure 2: Graphical representation of the various definition for each type of stakeholder, from the typology defined by Digital skills for FAIR and open science

5.2. UCs work on connectors and impact study

This section presents the UCs through screenshots of their connectors implemented during the EOSC FAIR-IMPACT project and standardised representation of the planification of their impact study (their issues and challenges are exposed and the means to assess the improvement due to their connectors).

Appendix Figure 3: Legend to each impact study representation (klaxoon board)

5.2.1. PHIS-AgroPortal

Appendix Figure 4 - Screenshot of the connector between PHIS and AgroPortal. The connector allows: (i) searching terms and filtering for specific-domain ontologies, (ii) selecting and creating new terms and (iii) mapping to related terms. Original figure from D4.6.

Appendix Figure 5: Representation of the PHIS-AgroPortal UC impact study. The main objectives and problems are set out and linked to the means of assessing the improvement brought about by the proposed solutions. The UC describes what is planned to be done.

5.2.2. LifeWatchDP&MDC-EcoPortal

Appendix Figure 6 - LifeWatch Italy Data Portal Keywords wizard.

In this figure, the search bar filled in by the term “biodiversity”, the results associated with this term and retrieved in various thesauri through the EcoPortal API. Many terms, according to the search, are proposed to the user, who can make a choice by consulting the information associated with the terms via the icon “i”. Original figure from D4.6.

Appendix Figure 7: Representation of the LifeWatch DP&MDC-EcoPortal UC impact study. The main objectives and problems are set out and linked to the means of assessing the improvement brought about by the proposed solutions. The UC describes what is planned to be done.

5.2.3. DANS Data Stations

Appendix Figure 8 - The process of term selection in DANS Data Stations. Original figure from D4.6.

Appendix Figure 9: Representation of the DANS Data Station UC impact study. The main objectives and problems are set out and linked to the means of assessing the improvement brought about by the proposed solutions. The UC describes what is planned to be done.

5.2.4. EaSyData-EarthPortal

Appendix Figure 10 - User interface showing use of the EaSy Data - EarthPortal connector. An additional button has been added to the Keywords field, providing the user the ability to query the EarthPortal for term suggestions and pick the relevant ones. Original figure from D4.6.

Appendix Figure 11: Representation of the EaSyData-EarthPortal UC impact study. The main objectives and problems are set out and linked to the means of assessing the improvement brought about by the proposed solutions. The UC describes what is planned to be done.

5.2.5. Recherche Data Gouv-AgroPortal

The image shows the Recherche Data Gouv-AgroPortal interface. At the top, it features the logos for 'The Dataverse Project' and the French Republic ('RÉPUBLIQUE FRANÇAISE'). Below these is the 'recherche.data.gouv.fr' logo and the 'Data INRAE' logo. The main section is titled 'Create a collection or a dataset → feeding metadata (keywords)'. A search box contains the text 'arabidopsis', and a dropdown menu shows several results, with 'Arabidopsis - INRAE Thesaurus (INRAETHES)' selected. To the right of the dropdown, a callout box labeled 'Unique search box' lists three bullet points: 'Search a term in AgroPortal via API', 'Import term, URIs, Vocabulary', and 'Same ID for all languages'. Below the search box, four metadata fields are displayed: 'Term' (Arabidopsis), 'Term URI' (http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/), 'Controlled Vocabulary Name' (INRAETHES), and 'Controlled Vocabulary URL' (http://opendata.inrae.fr/thesaurusINRAE/).

Appendix Figure 12 - Representation of Recherche Data Gouv-AgroPortal connector.
 In the metadata record, the search bar allows users to type a keyword, here “association”. With autocompletion, thanks to the connector, AgroPortal API retrieves term-related information, such as term, URI, vocabulary, URL, synonyms and, traduction. Original figure from D4.6.

Appendix Figure 13: Representation of the Recherche Data Gouv-AgroPortal UC impact study. The main objectives and problems are set out and linked to the means of assessing the improvement brought about by the proposed solutions. The UC describes what is planned to be done.

5.2.6. IVOA Astronomy

The screenshot shows the 'Browse' page of the OntoPortal. The header includes the OntoPortal logo and navigation links: Ontologies, Search, Annotator, Recommender, Mappings, Login, and Support. The main content area is titled 'Browse' and includes a search bar and a 'Showing 42 of 42 Sort: Popular' dropdown. On the left, there are several filter panels: 'Submit New Ontology', 'Entry Type' (with 'Ontology (42)' selected), 'Uploaded in the Last' (with a dropdown menu), 'Category', 'Group', and 'Format' (with 'OWL (34)', 'SKOS (7)', and 'UMLS (1)' options). The main list displays four ontologies:

- Unified Astronomy Thesaurus (UAT)**: 2,373 concepts. Description: "This Unified Astronomy Thesaurus (UAT) is an open, interoperable and community-supported thesaurus which unifies the existing divergent and isolated Astronomy & Astrophysics thesauri into a single high-quality, freely-available open thesaurus formalizing astronomical concepts and their inter-relationships." Upload date: 6/20/24.
- PDS4 Information Model Classes (PDS4-IM-1L00)**: 221 classes. Description: "NASA PDS4 Information Model Classes." Upload date: 11/9/23.
- IHDEA-TREPS-FRAMES (TREPSCOORDS)**: 78 classes. Description: "A collection of reference frames used by the CDDP/TREPS tool (https://treps.irap.omp.eu)." Upload date: 2/28/24.
- Astronomical Subject Keywords (2013) (ASTROKW)**: 394 concepts. Description: "The editors of many astronomy journals (ApJ, AJ, A&A, MNRAS, PASP, PASJ, and RMxAA) have adopted these subject keywords as a means of classifying articles in the journals." Upload date: 4/12/24.

Appendix figure 14: Screenshot of the Astronomy OntoPortal instance, developed and enriched during the EOSC FAIR-IMPACT project. This instance was created to implement a connector in the IVOA metadata repository.

Appendix Figure 15: Representation of the IVOA Astronomy UC impact study. The main objectives and problems are set out and linked to the means of assessing the improvement brought about by the proposed solutions. The UC describes what is planned to be done.

5.2.7. AnaEE-AgroPortal

Appendix Figure 16- SemData user interface with AgroPortal connector (mockup). To enrich the metadata record with additional keywords, users can manually search for new concepts through the SemData interface. The user starts writing keywords and the AgroPortal API call proposes several candidate terms, especially from AnaeeThes (as the default SA). He can select one or more of these concepts and add them to the metadata record. Original figure from D4.6.

Appendix Figure 17: Representation of the AnaEE-AgroPortal UC impact study. The main objectives and problems are set out and linked to the means of assessing the improvement brought about by the proposed solutions. The UC describes what is planned to be done.

5.2.8. Archeo-AMU

Appendix Figure 18 - OpenTheso Graphical User Interface for adding new SA from PACTOLS within EPICHERCHELL. Original figure from D4.6.

Appendix Figure 19: Representation of the ArcheoAMU UC impact study. The main objectives and problems are set out and linked to the means of assessing the improvement brought about by the proposed solutions. The UC describes what is planned to be done.

5.2.9. Identifiers.org-ROR.org

Institution details

This section of the form collects the information of the institution that runs the first provider being registered in the new namespace being requested. Examples are EMBL-EBI, Kyoto University or NCBI.

ROR ID: ← User fills this
The ROR ID of the organization. Example: <https://ror.org/02catss52>.

Name: ✓
The name of the institution that runs the provider. Example: European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge, UK.

Description: ✓
Short description of the institution in one or more sentences. Example: The European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) is the part of EMBL dedicated to big data and online services.

Home URL: ✓
A valid URL for the homepage of the institution. Example: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/>.

Location: ✓
The home country of the institution.

Information collected from ROR API (indicated by red arrows pointing to Name, Description, Home URL, and Location)

Appendix Figure 20 - Identifiers.org metadata record fill in for institution name space.
 Data depositors need to retrieve institute ROR ID from the ROR.org register and fill in the dedicated field, related information is collected from the ROR API and added to the record. Information is updated as long as the ROR ID is identical. Original figure from D4.6.

Appendix Figure 21: Representation of the Identifier.org-ROR.org UC impact study. The main objectives and problems are set out and linked to the means of assessing the improvement brought about by the proposed solutions. The UC describes what is planned to be done.

5.3. Dataverse Sorting results

```
dvName^400
authorName^180
dvSubject^190
dvDescription^180
dvAffiliation^170
title^130
subject^120
keyword^110
topicClassValue^100
dsDescriptionValue^90
authorAffiliation^80
publicationCitation^60
producerName^50
fileName^30
fileDescription^30
variableLabel^20
variableName^10
```

Appendix Figure 22: Weight of each metadata in the search results in the Dataverse repositories, provided by the search engine (Solr⁴⁹, which use Lucène⁵⁰). Notice that “keyword” contains the value of “keyword value”, “keyword URI”, “keyword vocabulary”, and “keyword vocabulary URL”.

⁴⁹ <https://solr.apache.org/>

⁵⁰ <https://lucene.apache.org/>